

IMAGE OF ANIMALS IN THE WORKS OF TOGAY MURAD.**Nazarova Orozkhol.**nazarovaorozxol@gmail.com

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Annotation; This article discusses the unique customs, emotions, and beautiful feelings of the Surkhan oasis.

Key words: Surkhan, folk, tradition, epic, drum, dress, tum or, behavior, horse, tarlan, feelings - brothers.

ОБРАЗ ЖИВОТНЫХ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ ТОГАЯ МУРАДА.

Аннотация; В этой статье рассматриваются уникальные обычаи, эмоции и прекрасные чувства Сурханского оазиса.

Ключевые слова: Сурхан, народ, традиция, эпос, барабан, платье, тумор, поведение, конь, тарлан, чувства-братья.

Let's not leave the profession of our ancestors on the ground. What does Kal have, he has an iron comb. I have a comb...

I'm excited! I took my drum and started my story. In my story, there was a wedding in the Surkhan oasis, tulips bloomed in the fields, trumpets played, guests came from all over the world...

The horse became epic;
Have a lot of children
You have a thousand amulets,
I look at your body
You have a lot to do.

There is a saying in SURKHAN:
"If you buy a horse, take it from Obakli,
If you get a wife, take it from Irgali."

The essence of this is that horse means giant, Horse means vastness. Horse does not know what distance is, it does not know what territory is. The horse runs in the

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steppes even in the harsh winter. It will be a horse that trembles. Its armpits will be stretched, its chest will be wide.

Obogli is such a steppe. There is a girl in Irgali. Irgaly's daughters will mature. She will put on the unworn seventh kalish. Her waist will be strong and full. If she hugs Irgaly's daughters, she will be full of sheep. Irgaly's daughters have seen

the child will also be Alpomishkelbat. The reason is that Alpomish passed in the same Irgali. Brothers, although the horse has a similar character, although he is more understanding, although he is more handsome, still ,horse, own horse! A four-legged animal! An animal with a tail!

What is abundant in the world! There are plenty of four-legged animals. Is it possible to bring a four-legged animal into the country as it is? It won't happen! In any case, can it be done like this? No! First of all, it is necessary to make a four-legged animal a horse! It is not enough to ride a four-legged animal. Not everyone can handle a tailed animal! To make a four-legged animal a horse, first of all, it must be in the heart! First of all, it is necessary to have a body!

If you feed the horses, feed them

Carry water from afar,

Don't break the bait,

Add the fruit to the feed.

A storyteller tells a story. If he makes a mistake, he stops.

A poet finishes a book. If there is something unpleasant in his book, the poet erases it with a pen and makes it pleasant.

The artist draws a picture. In a photo, a person's eyebrow does not look like an eyebrow. A horse's mane does not look like a mane. The painter immediately makes the eyebrows of a man, and the mane of a horse.

A rider cannot fix a horse!

When a four-legged animal becomes a horse...haha, when it becomes a horse...whatever it finds a behavior, it stays in that behavior. if he learns, everything stays in his body and in his brain.

After that, if the rider says that he will fix the horse, he will hurt himself. The horse cannot be fixed!

Brethren, a good horse and a rider will become a building from the intelligence!
Sarah will be a horse rider from the heart! [1]

I threw Tarlon away,
I tied it to a high manger in the stable.
I closed the hole through which the manure was removed with a pipe at night,
and opened it during the day...

Or;

I started feeding Tarlon with barley feed.

I gave four kilos of barley feed in Azan.

I fed six kilos of barley in the afternoon.

I fed five kilos of barley in the evening.

I gave salt in my palm.

Tarlon gulps and eats the salt.

I caught white sugar in my palm.

Tarlon took the sugar with his lips.

Now I salted the slaughtered sheep's tail.

Brothers, heaven on a horse is hell at the mouth!

Uncle Murad's stories are purely national Uzbek stories. The people described in the stories of Uncle Murad are known to be Uzbeks, even if you wear the clothes of a different nation.

Until now, if you put on a hat with an indistinct appearance, if you put on a Russian Karakol papakh, if you put on an Azerbaijani telpak, if you put on a shirt with a Kazakh collar on the shoulders, and if you wear a shirt with embroidery on the shoulders, the main characters of our stories have become the main characters of our stories. "It's not knowing them, it's stupidity, it's stupidity."

Here is how he describes the horse in "The Night the Horse Neighed":

"Brothers, what will a gray horse look like? It will be as white as soap. If it is in the ancestor's blood, at the age of nine, small grains will appear on the body of the gray horse. From then on, Tarlon will be a horse, not a greyhound. Tarlon is a horse

The famous writer Shukur Kholmirezayev, who is a real devotee of our national literature, remembers like this; "By the way, last year I wrote a story about the year of the horse

you know I'm done. It didn't happen by itself. J. Do you remember London's work about the wolf? After reading it five or six times, I began to think. Why is there no such

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work in Uzbek literature? J. A wolf is a fetish for London, and a horse is dear to my people. Thus, the story "Year of the Horse" was created. [2]

Thus, the stories of Uncle Murad brought the unique breath of the Surkhan Valley into our literature, and aroused sincere love in our hearts for the cheerful, humble anti-herdsmen and gardeners. imbued with a folk spirit reminiscent of his mother. The fact that Uncle Murad himself grew up in the beautiful valleys and endless pastures given by the Alpomishva Barchins can be felt from his vocabulary, writing style and unique voice. The ability to work is one of the best qualities of a young writer's pen.

1; /Selected works; T. Murad.-T; East, 2008. J.I.; stories./

2; Selected works volume III stories T; "East" page 502 Sh. Kholmirezayev./